

Effect of Concept Mapping Strategy On Senior Secondary School Students' Performance in Mathematics in Ekiti State, Nigeria

Author(s), Prof. Popoola Abiodun A., Mr. O. A. OJO

Abstract:

The study examined the effect of concept mapping strategy on senior secondary school students' performance in Mathematics in Ekiti State. The study adopted the quasi-experimental of pre-test, post-test design. The population for the study consisted of all the Senior Secondary School two (S.S.S.II) students in all public Secondary Schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The sample consisted of 151 S.S.S. II found in intact classes of the six schools that were selected for the study. The sample was selected using multistage sampling procedure. Mathematical Performance Test (MPT) was used to collect the needed data for this study. The instrument consisted of 25 items to examine the performance of students in Mathematics. The reliability of the instrument was established through a field testing which involved 30 senior secondary school students who were not part of the study. The internal consistency of the instrument was then ascertained using Cronbach Alpha which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.805. The experimental procedure for the study was in three stages: the pre-treatment, the treatment and the post-treatment stage. The data collected were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. All hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. It was revealed that concept mapping strategy was more effective and reliable than the conventional method. Students performed better when exposed to

EASIJ

Accepted 4 August 2022
Published 27 August 2022
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7029825

concept mapping strategy than exposing them to conventional method in Mathematics. It was recommended among others that concept mapping strategy should be adopted as a means of instruction during Mathematics class. This will enable students to critically think and also allow students pay attention during Mathematics instruction.

Keywords: Concept Mapping, Performance, Students, Mathematics,

About Author

Author(s):

Prof. Popoola Abiodun A.

Department of Science Education,
Faculty of Education,
Ekiti State University, Ado – Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

And

Mr. O. A. OJO

Department of Science Education,
School of Science Education, College of Education,
Bamidele Olumilua University of Education, Science and Technology,
Ikere – Ekiti, Ekiti State, Nigeria.

Introduction

Globally, mathematics is regarded as one of the most important subjects in the school curriculum worldwide. It is seen as a subject that has direct correlation with other subjects, particularly science and technology (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2013; Popoola & Olofin, 2020). Mathematics remains one of the most difficult subjects in schools as perceived by students. There is general impression that Mathematics is difficult by its very nature and because of this impression, majority of students have phobia for it (Ampadu, 2012; Ojimba, 2012; Saad, et al., 2014). For students to participate fully in the society, they must learn Mathematics with understanding, connect mathematical idea and reason mathematically (Hollebrands, et al., 2010).

A lack of sufficient mathematical skill and understanding affects the ability to think critically in life and also to make proper career decisions. Thus, mathematics plays a very vital role in the modernisation of this civilisation. Mathematics is everywhere and it influence the everyday lives of people. A good score in mathematics is also a prerequisite for most courses in science-learning colleges and universities. Mathematics lays the foundation of scientific technical knowledge for industrial and technological advancement (Popoola, 2014). Despite the importance of Mathematics, many students are still not getting their feet in the subject. West African Examination Council (WAEC) recorded the average performance of candidates in Mathematics from 2016 – 2020 where an average of 51% of the candidates who sat for the examination failed Mathematics.

The performance of students in Mathematics could be attributed to certain factors which include mastery of the subject matter by the teacher, instructional (both human and material) resources, teaching strategy among others. The researcher observed that most common method used by Mathematics teachers in secondary schools is the conventional method which may not have meaningful impact on the performance of students in the subject like Mathematics. The researcher considers it necessary to explore the efficacies of concept mapping strategy on students' performance of Mathematics.

Concept mapping process externalizes the concepts in the student's existing knowledge structure; it is possible to identify misconceptions, incongruities and weaknesses in that existing knowledge structure. Therefore, this study uses concept mapping strategy with a view to finding how it can enhance students' academic performance in and attitude towards Mathematics. It is a meta-learning technique for assisting learners to organize information about concepts in a meaningful manner in order to facilitate meaningful learning.

Concept mapping is a structured process focused on a topic or construct of interest involving input from one or more participants that produces an interpretable pictorial view of their ideas and concepts and how these are interrelated (Yusuf, 2009). In concept maps, ideas are arranged hierarchically with the super ordinate concepts at the top of the map, and subordinate at the bottom which are less inclusive than higher ones. Rao (2015) stated that concept mapping strategy is hinged on the fact that concepts do not exist in isolation, but rather are inter-related with others to make meaning. The organization of new concepts, information or learning tasks in a manner that show how these concepts are interrelated may help the learner to make mental connections between these ideas.

Concept maps are considered to be potentially powerful problem-solving tools (Jonassen 2014). From this aspect, concept maps become a valuable tool for the development of

problem solving abilities. Problem solving is a complex activity which involves a variety of components that include concepts, rules and principles. However, it also involves structural knowledge and metacognition skills (Jonassen 2014). Mapping provides opportunity for convergent thinking and Concept mapping enhances meaningful understanding of scientific concepts.

Akinjiola (2010) also conducted a study on effect of concept mapping instructional strategy on junior secondary school students' performance in ratio and proportion in mathematics. The result showed that there was a significant difference in the mean score of male and female student when taught ratio and proportion using concept- mapping instructional strategy in favour of female. Githae, et al. (2015) suggest that a learner can use concept mapping to extract relationships between key concepts because knowledge is broken down into simple and more easily understandable parts.

Udeani and Okafor (2012) carried out a research on the effect of concept mapping instructional strategy on the Biology achievement of senior secondary school learners. A 30 – item multiple pre-test and post-test were used to collect the data and a t-test was used to test the hypotheses. Analysis of the post-test scores indicated that the group taught by the concept mapping instructional strategy performed significantly ($p < 0.05$) better than their expository group counterparts.

In view of the above, the study examined the effect of concept mapping strategy on senior secondary school students' performance in Mathematics in Ekiti State. The study specifically:

1. examined the performance of students in Mathematics before and after treatment; and
2. examined the difference in the pre-test and post-test mean scores of students exposed to concept mapping strategy and conventional method;

Research Question

This research question was raised for the study:

1. What is the performance difference of students in Mathematics of students exposed to concept mapping strategy and conventional method before and after treatment?

Research Hypotheses

The following null-hypotheses were formulated to guide the study:

1. There is no significant difference in the pre-test mean scores of students in Mathematics exposed to concept mapping strategy and conventional method.
2. There is no significant difference in the post-test mean scores of students in Mathematics exposed to concept mapping strategy and conventional method.
3. There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test mean scores of students exposed to concept mapping strategy and conventional method.

Methodology

The study adopted the quasi-experimental of pre-test, post-test design. The population for the study consisted of all the Senior Secondary School two (S.S.S. II) students in all public Secondary Schools in Ekiti State, Nigeria. The sample consisted of 151 S.S.S. II found in intact classes of the six schools that were selected for the study. The sample was selected using multistage sampling procedure.

Mathematical Performance Test (MPT) was used to collect the needed data for this study. The instrument consisted of 25 items to examine the performance of students in Mathematics. The reliability of the instrument was established through a field testing which involved 30

senior secondary school students who were not part of the study. The internal consistency of the instrument was then ascertained using Cronbach Alpha. This yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.805, which was considered high enough and reliable for the research.

The experimental procedure for the study was in three stages: the pre-treatment stage (one week), the treatment stage (five weeks) and the post-treatment stage (one week). Seven weeks were used altogether for the whole exercise. The data collected were analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The research questions raised were answered using descriptive statistics involving frequency counts, mean, standard deviation and percentages while the hypotheses postulated were tested using inferential statistics involving t-test and Univariate Analysis of Variance (two-way). Decisions were taken at 0.05 level of significance.

Results

Research Question 1: What is the performance difference of students in Mathematics of students exposed to concept mapping strategy and conventional method before and after treatment?

In answering the question, mean scores of students in Mathematics before and after being exposed to treatments were computed and compared. The result is presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Mean and standard deviation of pre-test and post-test scores of students exposed to concept mapping strategy and conventional method

Strategies	Test	N	Mean	S.D	Mean Diff.
Concept Mapping	Pre Test	74	47.31	9.78	31.75
	Post Test		79.06	7.09	
Conventional	Pre Test	77	46.94	10.19	9.22
	Post Test		56.16	9.81	
Total		151			

Table 1 revealed the performance of students in Mathematics before and after treatment. The performance of students exposed to concept mapping between pre-test and post-test scores is 31.75 while control group is 9.22. The graphical representation below further shows the more effective strategy in the teaching of Mathematics.

Figure i: Bar chart showing pre-test and post-test mean scores of students in Mathematics exposed to concept mapping strategy and conventional method

Test of Hypotheses

H₀1: There is no significant difference in the pre-test mean scores of students in Mathematics exposed to concept mapping strategy and conventional method.

In order to test the hypothesis, performance of students before treatment were collected from Mathematical Performance Test (MPT). T-test was used to compute difference in performance before treatment. The result is presented in Table 2.

Table 2: t-test Analysis for difference in the pre-test mean scores of students in Mathematics exposed to concept mapping strategy and conventional method

Variations	N	Mean	SD	Df	t _{cal}	P
Concept Mapping	74	47.31	9.78	149	0.228	0.814
Conventional	77	46.94	10.19			

P>0.05

Table 2 shows that the t-cal value of 0.2284 was not significant because the P value of 0.814 was greater than 0.05 significant point. This implies that null hypothesis is not rejected. Therefore, there is no significant difference in the pre-test mean scores of students in Mathematics exposed to concept mapping strategy and conventional method. The implication of this finding is that the students exposed to concept mapping strategy and conventional method were homogeneous at the commencement of the study.

H₀2: There is no significant difference in the post-test mean scores of students in Mathematics exposed to concept mapping strategy and conventional method.

In order to test the hypothesis, performance of students after treatment were collected from Mathematical Performance Test (MPT). T-test was used to compute difference in performance before treatment. The result is presented in Table 3.

Table 3: t-test Analysis for difference in the post-test mean scores of students exposed to concept mapping strategy and conventional method

Variations	N	Mean	SD	df	t _{cal}	P
Concept Mapping	74	79.06	7.09	149	16.488*	0.000
Conventional Method	77	56.16	9.81			

*P<0.05

Table 3 shows that the t-cal value of 16.488 was significant because the P value of 0.000 was less than 0.05 significant point. This implies that null hypothesis is rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference in the post-test mean scores of students in Mathematics exposed to concept mapping strategy and conventional method.

H₀₃: There is no significant difference in the pre-test and post-test mean scores of students exposed to concept mapping strategy and conventional method.

In order to test the hypothesis, performance of students before and after treatment were collected from Mathematical Performance Test (MPT). Analysis of Covariance was used to compute difference in performance before and after treatment in the groups. The result is presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Analysis of Covariance for difference in the pre-test and post-test mean scores of students in Mathematics in the groups

Source	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	3093.603	2	1546.802	226.704	.000
Intercept	921.929	1	921.929	135.121	.000
Pre-Test	9.511	1	9.511	1.394	.548
Groups	1101.271	1	1101.271	161.406*	.000
Error	1009.823	148	6.823		
Total	265130.718	151			
Corrected Total	5340.924	150			

a. R Squared = .807 (Adjusted R Squared = .800)

The result presented in table 4 shows that there is a significant difference in the pre-test and post-test mean scores of students exposed to concept mapping strategy and conventional method as $F_{cal} = 161.406$, $P = 0.000 < 0.05$. This result led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. By implication, there is significant difference in the pre-test and post-test mean scores of students exposed to concept mapping strategy and conventional method. In order to find out the more probable effective strategy, Multiple Classification Analysis (MCA) was carried out. The result is shown in Table 5.

Table 5: Multiple Classification Analysis (MCA) of students' performance in Mathematics by treatment

Variable + Category	N	Unadjusted Dev'n	Eta ²	Adjusted for Independent + Covariate	Beta
Grand Mean = 67.38					

Concept Mapping	74	11.68	.79	11.62	.51
Conventional	77	-11.22		-11.35	
Multiple R					.898
Multiple R²					.807

The result in Table 5 shows the Multiple Classification Analysis (MCA) of students' performance in Mathematics by treatment. It reveals that, with a grand mean of 67.38, students exposed to concept mapping had higher adjusted mean score of 79.06(67.38+11.68) than their counterparts exposed to conventional method 56.16(67.38+ (-11.22)). This implies that students exposed to concept mapping strategy performed better than students exposed to the conventional method. The treatment explained about 79% ($\text{Eta}^2 = 0.79$) of the observed variance in students' performance in Mathematics. The two treatment strategies accounted for 80.7% ($R^2 = 0.807$) contribution to academic performance of the students in Mathematics.

Discussion

The findings of the study descriptively revealed that the performance of students exposed to concept mapping between pre-test and post-test scores is 31.75 while control group is 9.22. The findings of the study revealed that there was no significant difference in the pre-test mean scores of students in Mathematics exposed to concept mapping strategy and conventional method. This finding established the homogeneity of the two groups involved in the study prior to the experiment. In other words, it could be said that the knowledge baseline for the two groups involved in the study are equal. Consequently, any significant difference recorded afterwards would not be ascribed to chance, but to the specific treatment applied.

It was however revealed that there was significant difference in the post-test mean scores of students exposed to concept mapping strategy and conventional method. Students exposed to concept mapping performed better than students exposed to the conventional method. This finding is in consonance with the findings of Akinjiola (2010), Akeju, et al. (2011), Udeani and Okafor (2012), Carroll (2012) and Githae, et al. (2015) and as they concluded that concept mapping instructional strategy significantly impact students' performance in Mathematics and science related subjects.

Conclusion

Considering the findings of this study, it was concluded that, concept mapping strategy was more effective and reliable than the conventional method. Students performed better when exposed to concept mapping strategy than exposing them to conventional method in Mathematics.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Concept mapping strategy should be adopted as a means of instruction during Mathematics class. This will enable students to critically think and also allow students pay attention during Mathematics instruction.

2. The State Ministry of Education should expose Mathematics teachers to appropriate in-service training on the use of concept mapping strategy as this will enhance teachers' professional competencies in their jobs.

References

- Akinjiola, E. Y. (2010). *Effect of concept-mapping instructional strategy on junior secondary school students' performance in mathematics in Ilorin, Nigeria* (Unpublished M. Ed Thesis). University of Ilorin, Ilorin.
- Ampadu, E. (2012). Students' perceptions of their teachers' teaching of mathematics: the case of Ghana. *International online Journal of Educational sciences*, 2012, 4(2) 351-388.
- Federal Republic Nigeria (FRN) (2013). *National Policy on Education*. Lagos: NERDC Press.
- Githae, R. W., Keraro, F. N. and Wachanga S. W. (2015). Effects of collaborative concept mapping teaching approach on secondary school students' achievement in biology in Nakuru North Sub-County, Kenya. *Global Research Journal of Education*.
- Hollebrands, K.F., Conner , A.M., & Smith , R.C (2010). The Nature of Arguments Provided by College Geometry Students With Access to Technology While Solving Problems. *Journal for Research in Mathematics Education*, 41(4), 324–350.
- Jonassen, D. H. (2014). *Learning to solve problems. An Instructional design guide*. San Francisco, CA: Pfeiffer.
- Ojimba, D. P. (2012). Strategies for Teaching and Sustaining Mathematics as an Indispensable Tool for Technological Development in Nigeria. <http://www.mcser.org/images/stories/MJSS-Special>.
- Popoola, A.A. (2014). Secondary School Mathematics Teachers' skill and Students' Achievements using Innovative and Model Teaching Approaches. *Journal of Research & Method in Education (IORS-JRME)*. 4(3), 06-15.
- Popoola, A.A. and Olofin, S.O. (2020). Influence of Teacher Characteristics on Academic Performance of Senior Secondary School Students in Mathematics in Three Geo-Political Zones of Nigeria. *Euro Afro Studies International Journal*, 1(2), 13 – 23. DOI: www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3700220
- Rao, M. P. (2015). Effect of Concept Mapping In Science Achievement Cognitive Skills And Attitude. Regional Institute of Education India. Retrieved On 26th June 2020 From www.freepateintsonline.com/article/schoolscience.
- Saad, T.U, Adamu, A. and Sadiq, A.M. (2014). The causes of poor performance in mathematics among public senior secondary school students in Azare metropolis of Bauchi State, Nigeria. *Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 4(6), 329 – 341
- Yusuf K.B. (2009). Effect of concept mapping strategy on secondary school students' academic achievement in biology in Obafemi Owode Local Government, Ogun Masters' Student Project

Cite this article:

Author(s), Prof. Popoola Abiodun A., Mr. O. A. OJO, (2022). “ Effect of Concept Mapping Strategy On Senior Secondary School Students’ Performance in Mathematics in Ekiti State, Nigeria”, **Name of the Journal:** Euro Afro Studies International Journal, (EASIJ.COM), P, 86 – 95. DOI: www.doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7029825 , Special Issue, Issue: 8, Vol.: 4, Article: 8, Month: August, Year: 2022. Retrieved from <https://www.easij.com/all-issues/>

Published By

AND

ThoughtWares Consulting & Multi Services International (TWCMSI)

